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The General First Zagreb Matrix of a Graph

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce the concept of the general first Zagreb matrix of a graph. Suppose G is a graph with n vertices and d_i the degree of its i -th vertex v_i . The general first Zagreb matrix of G is defined as the square matrix of order n whose (i, j) -entry is equal to $d_i^{r-1} + d_j^{r-1}$ if the i -th and j -th vertices of G are adjacent and zero otherwise, where r is an integer with $r \geq 2$. In this paper, we present some spectral results on the general first Zagreb matrix of a graph.

Keywords: Zagreb index of a graph, the general first Zagreb matrix of a graph, the energy of a graph, the general first Zagreb energy of a graph.

AMS subject classification: 05C50, 05C09

1 Introduction

Throughout this paper, all graphs will be assumed simple. If G is such a graph with n -vertices and m -edges, then G will be called an (n, m) -graph. Let $G =$

$(V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with vertex set $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ and edge set $E(G)$ with $|E(G)| = m$. The degree of vertex v_i in the graph G is denoted by $d(v_i)$, where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. We use $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$ to denote the eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix, denoted $A(G)$, of G . It is well known that the determinant of $A(G)$, denoted $\det(A(G))$, is equal to $\prod_{i=1}^n \lambda_i$. For an $n \times n$ complex matrix M with eigenvalues $\nu_1, \nu_2, \dots, \nu_n$, the spread of M , denoted $s(M)$, is defined as $s(M) := \max_{i,j} |\nu_i - \nu_j|$ and the energy of M , denoted $E(M)$, is defined as $E(G) := \sum_{i=1}^n |\nu_i - \frac{DS(M)}{n}|$, where $DS(M)$ is the sum of the diagonal entries in M . The first Zagreb index and the second Zagreb index were introduced by Gutman and Trinajstić in [10]. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index and second Zagreb index are defined as $\sum_{i=1}^n d^2(v_i) = \sum_{v_i v_j \in E} (d(v_i) + d(v_j))$ and $\sum_{v_i v_j \in E} d(v_i)d(v_j)$, respectively. For a positive integer $r \geq 2$, we defined $M_r = \sum_{i=1}^n d^r(v_i) = \sum_{v_i v_j \in E} (d^{r-1}(v_i) + d^{r-1}(v_j))$ and $R_r = \sum_{v_i v_j \in E} d^{r-1}(v_i)d^{r-1}(v_j)$.

In [18], Rad, Jahanbani, and Gutman introduced the first Zagreb matrix and the second Zagreb matrix of a graph G as follows. The first Zagreb matrix, denoted $Z^{(1)}(G)$, of G is defined as the square matrix of order n whose (i, j) -entry is equal to $d_i + d_j$ if the i -th and j -th vertices of G are adjacent and zero otherwise; The second Zagreb matrix, denoted $Z^{(2)}(G)$, of G is defined as the square matrix of order n whose (i, j) -entry is equal to $d_i d_j$ if the i -th and j -th vertices of G are adjacent and zero otherwise.

Motivated by the concepts of the first Zagreb matrix and the second matrix of a graph, we introduce the concepts of the general first Zagreb matrix and general second Zagreb matrix of a graph G as follows. The general first Zagreb matrix of G , denoted $Z_1^r(G)$, is defined as the square matrix of order n whose (i, j) -entry is equal to $d_i^{r-1} + d_j^{r-1}$ if the i -th and j -th vertices of G are adjacent and zero otherwise, where r is an integer with $r \geq 2$. The general second Zagreb matrix of G , denoted $Z_2^r(G)$, is defined as the square matrix of order n whose (i, j) -entry is equal to $d_i^{r-1} d_j^{r-1}$ if the i -th and j -th vertices of G are adjacent and zero otherwise, where r is an integer with $r \geq 2$. Obviously, $Z^{(1)}(G) = Z_1^2(G)$ and $Z^{(2)}(G) = Z_2^2(G)$.

Obviously, $Z_1^r(G)$ is a symmetric matrix with all the diagonal entries are equal to zero. Its eigenvalues, denoted $\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_n$, are real and we arrange them in non-increasing order. In this paper, we present some results on the eigenvalues, spread, and energy of the general first Zagreb matrix of a graph.

2 Preliminaries and known results

In this section, we shall present some previously known results that will be needed in Section 3. Denote by N_k the k -th spectral moment of the general first Zagreb

matrix Z_1^r , namely,

$$N_k = \sum_{j=1}^n \mu_j^k \tag{1}$$

Recall that N_k is equal to the trace, denoted $tr((Z_1^r)^k)$, of $(Z_1^r)^k$. Then we have the following lemma.

Lemma 1. *Let G be a graph with n vertices. Then*

$$(i) \quad N_0 = n \tag{2}$$

$$(ii) \quad N_1 = tr(Z_1^r) = 0 \tag{3}$$

$$(iii) \quad N_2 = tr((Z_1^r)^2) = 2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r \tag{4}$$

Proof. (i) Obviously, $N_0 = n$. (ii) By definition, the diagonal elements of Z_1^r are equal to zero. Therefore the trace of Z_1^r is zero. (iii)

$$\begin{aligned} N_2 &= tr((Z_1^r)^2) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (d^{r-1}(v_i) + d^{r-1}(v_j))^2 = 2 \sum_{v_i v_j \in E} (d^{r-1}(v_i) + d^{r-1}(v_j))^2 \\ &= 2 \left(\sum_{v_i v_j \in E} (d^{2r-2}(v_i) + d^{2r-2}(v_j)) + 2 \sum_{v_i v_j \in E} (d^{r-1}(v_i)d^{r-1}(v_j)) \right) = 2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r. \end{aligned}$$

□

Now, we recall two discrete inequalities for real number sequences that will be used subsequently.

Lemma 2. [2] *(Chebishev inequality) Let $a_1 \leq a_2 \leq \dots \leq a_n$ and $b_1 \leq b_2 \leq \dots \leq b_n$ be real numbers. Then we have*

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n b_i \right) \leq n \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i,$$

equality occurs if and only if $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_n$ or $b_1 = b_2 = \dots = b_n$.

Lemma 3. [13] *Let $a_1, \dots, a_n$ be non-negative numbers. If $X = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i$ and $Y = \left(\prod_{i=1}^n a_i \right)^{1/n}$, then*

$$\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i < j} (\sqrt{a_i} - \sqrt{a_j})^2 \leq X - Y \leq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i < j} (\sqrt{a_i} - \sqrt{a_j})^2.$$

Remark 4. *For nonnegative $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ and $k \geq 2$,*

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i)^k \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \right)^{\frac{k}{2}}. \tag{5}$$

The following result appears in [11].

Lemma 5. (Rayleigh-Ritz) *If B is a real symmetric $n \times n$ matrix with eigenvalues $\lambda_1(B) \geq \lambda_2(B) \geq \dots \geq \lambda_n(B)$, then for any $X \in R^n$, ($X \neq 0$),*

$$\lambda_n(B)X^t X \leq X^t B X \leq \lambda_1(B)X^t X.$$

The left equality holds if and only if X is an eigenvector of B , corresponding to the smallest eigenvalue $\lambda_n(B)$. The right equality holds if and only if X is an eigenvector of B , corresponding to the largest eigenvalue $\lambda_1(B)$.

Using a proof which is similar to the proof for Theorem 3.14 on Page 88 in [3], we can prove the following theorem.

Lemma 6. *Let G be a graph. If the number of eigenvalues of $Z_1^r(G)$ which are greater than, less than, and equal to zero are respectively p , q and r . then*

$$\alpha \leq r + \min\{p, q\},$$

where α is the independence number of G .

In [14], a class of real polynomials $P_n(x) = x^n + a_1x^{n-1} + a_2x^{n-2} + a_3x^{n-3} + \dots + a_n$, denoted as $P_n(a_1, a_2)$, where a_1 and a_2 are fixed real numbers, was considered.

Remark 7. *For the roots $x_1 \geq x_2 \geq \dots \geq x_n$ of an arbitrary polynomial $P_n(x)$ from this class, the following values were introduced*

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i, \tag{6}$$

$$\Delta = n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^2. \tag{7}$$

Then upper and lower bounds for the polynomial roots, $x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, were determined in terms of the introduced values

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{x} + \frac{1}{n} \sqrt{\frac{\Delta}{n-1}} &\leq x_1 \leq \bar{x} + \frac{1}{n} \sqrt{(n-1)\Delta} \\ \sqrt{\frac{\Delta}{\left[\frac{n}{2}\right] \left[\frac{n+1}{2}\right]}} &\leq x_1 - x_n \leq \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta}{n}}. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

3 Main results and their proofs

We next prove the following lemma that will be needed for obtaining the upper bounds of the general first Zagreb energy.

Theorem 8. Let G be a connected graph with $n \geq 2$ vertices. Suppose $\mu_1 \geq \mu_2 \geq \dots \geq \mu_n$ are the eigenvalues of $Z_1^r(G)$. Then

$$\mu_n \leq \frac{2M_r(G)}{n} \leq \mu_1. \tag{9}$$

Proof. Applying Lemma 5 with $B = Z_1^r$ and $X = (1, 1, \dots, 1)^t$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} n\mu_n &\leq \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (d^{r-1}(v_i) + d^{r-1}(v_j)) \\ &= 2 \sum_{v_i v_j \in E} (d^{r-1}(v_i) + d^{r-1}(v_j)) = 2M_r(G) \leq n\mu_1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\mu_n \leq \frac{2M_r(G)}{n} \leq \mu_1. \tag{9}$$

□

By using Remark 6, we can obtain the following results relate the μ_1 and M_{2r-1} and R_r .

Theorem 9. Let G be a simple graph with $n \geq 2$, vertices. Then

$$\frac{1}{n} \sqrt{\frac{2n(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)}{n-1}} \leq \mu_1 \leq \frac{1}{n} \sqrt{2n(n-1)(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)}.$$

Proof. Let the characteristic polynomial of $Z_1^r(G)$ is the following:

$$\varphi_n(x) = \prod_{i=1}^n (x - \mu_i) = x^n + a_1x^{n-1} + a_2x^{n-2} + b_3x^{n-3} + \dots + b_n.$$

Since

$$a_1 = - \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i = 0$$

and

$$a_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \right)^2 - \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i^2 \right] = -(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r),$$

the polynomial $\varphi_n(x)$ belongs to a class of real polynomials $P_n(0, -(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r))$. Notice that

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i = 0$$

and

$$\Delta = n \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \right)^2 = 2n(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)$$

and Remark (7), we obtain the inequalities for μ_1 . □

Next, we present a bound for $E(Z_1^r(G))$ based on the spread of the general first Zagreb matrix of G .

Theorem 10. *For any connected graph G of order $n \geq 2$, we have*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \geq \frac{4(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)}{s(Z_1^r(G))}. \tag{10}$$

Proof. We apply the following inequality ([15], pp. 346): if y_i and b_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) be real numbers such that

$$\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i| = 1, \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^n y_i = 0,$$

then, we have

$$\left| \sum_{i=1}^n b_i y_i \right| \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\max_{1 \leq i \leq n} b_i - \min_{1 \leq i \leq n} b_i \right). \tag{11}$$

By Lemma 1, we have $\sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i = 0$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i^2 = 2(M_{2r-1} + 2R_{r-1})$. If we take $b_i = \mu_i$ and $y_i = \frac{\mu_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|}$, then clearly

$$\sum_{i=1}^n y_i = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|} = 0$$

and

$$\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i| = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|} = 1.$$

Thus the conditions for inequality (11) are satisfied and we have

$$\left| \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|} \right| \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\max_{1 \leq i \leq n} (\mu_i) - \min_{1 \leq i \leq n} (\mu_i) \right).$$

We deduce from Lemma 1 and the aforementioned inequality that

$$\frac{2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r}{E(Z_1^r(G))} \leq \frac{1}{2} (\mu_1 - \mu_n),$$

which leads to the desired bound for $E(Z_1^r(G))$. □

In the following, we present results relating the general first Zagreb energy with M_{2r-1} and R_r .

Theorem 11. *Let G be a graph with n vertices. Then*

$$\sqrt{2(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)} \leq E(Z_1^r(G)) \leq \sqrt{2n(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)}.$$

Proof. By Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, for real numbers a_i and b_i , we have

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i\right)^2 \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i^2\right)\left(\sum_{i=1}^n b_i^2\right).$$

For $a_i = 1$, $b_i = |\mu_i|$, we have

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|\right)^2 \leq n\left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2\right) = n\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_i)^2 = n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r),$$

the above equality implies that

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \leq \sqrt{2n(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)}.$$

Now for the lower bound of $E(Z_1^r(G))$, we can easily obtain the inequality

$$(E(Z_1^r(G)))^2 = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|\right)^2 \geq \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 = (2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r).$$

This completes the proof of the theorem. □

In the next theorem, we obtain a lower bound for the general Zagreb energy.

Theorem 12. *Let G be a connected graph with n vertices. Then*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \geq \sqrt{2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r + n(n-1)|\det(Z_1^r(G))|^{\frac{2}{n}}}.$$

Proof. By the definition of the general Zagreb energy, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (E(Z_1^r(G)))^2 &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|\right)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} |\mu_i| |\mu_j| \\ &= 2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r + 2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} |\mu_i| |\mu_j| \\ &= 2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r + \sum_{i \neq j} |\mu_i| |\mu_j|. \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

By the inequality for arithmetic and geometric means, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i \neq j} |\mu_i| |\mu_j| &\geq \left(\prod_{i \neq j} |\mu_i| |\mu_j|\right)^{\frac{1}{n(n-1)}} = \left(\prod_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^{2(n-1)}\right)^{\frac{1}{n(n-1)}} \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^{\frac{2}{n}} = |\det(Z_1^r(G))|^{\frac{2}{n}} \end{aligned}$$

the above inequality and (12) leads to the desired result. □

Theorem 13. *If G is a graph of order $n \geq 3$, then*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \geq \sqrt{2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r + n(n-1)|\det(Z_1^r(G))|^{\frac{2}{n}} + \frac{4 \sum_{i < j \leq k < l} (\sqrt{|\mu_i||\mu_j|} - \sqrt{|\mu_k||\mu_l|})^2}{(n+1)(n-2)}}.$$

Proof. By definition, we have

$$(E(Z_1^r(G)))^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 + 2 \sum_{i < j} |\mu_i||\mu_j|. \tag{13}$$

Setting $N = \frac{n(n-1)}{2}$ and

$$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N) = (|\mu_1||\mu_2|, |\mu_1||\mu_3|, \dots, |\mu_1||\mu_n|, |\mu_2||\mu_3|, \dots, |\mu_2||\mu_n|, \dots, |\mu_{n-1}||\mu_n|)$$

in Lemma 3, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} |\mu_i||\mu_j| &\geq \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \left(\prod_{i=1}^n |\mu_i| \right)^{2/n} \\ &\quad + \frac{2}{n^2 - n - 2} \sum_{i < j \leq k < l} \left(\sqrt{|\mu_i||\mu_j|} - \sqrt{|\mu_k||\mu_l|} \right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

yielding

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} |\mu_i||\mu_j| &\geq n(n-1) (\det(Z_1^r(G)))^{2/n} \\ &\quad + \frac{4}{(n+1)(n-2)} \sum_{i < j \leq k < l} \left(\sqrt{|\mu_i||\mu_j|} - \sqrt{|\mu_k||\mu_l|} \right)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Combining the above inequality with (13) leads to the desired inequality. □

Obviously, the bound of Theorem 13 is better than the bound of Theorem 12.

Next, we present an upper bound for the the general Zagreb energy.

Theorem 14. *Let G be a graph with n vertices. Then*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \leq \frac{2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r + n}{2}.$$

Proof. Let $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ and $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ be sequences of real numbers. and $c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n$ and $d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n$ are nonnegative. Then the following inequality is valid (see [6])

$$\sum_{i=1}^n d_i \sum_{i=1}^n c_i a_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \sum_{i=1}^n d_i b_i^2 \geq 2 \sum_{i=1}^n a_i c_i \sum_{i=1}^n b_i d_i. \tag{14}$$

For $a_i := |\mu_i|$, $b_i := c_i = d_i = 1$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, Inequality (14) becomes

$$\sum_{i=1}^n 1 \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n 1 \sum_{i=1}^n 1 \geq 2 \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i| \sum_{i=1}^n 1.$$

Therefore, by Equality (4) and the definition of the general Zagreb energy, we have the desired inequality. $\square$

In the next theorem, we determine an upper bound on the general Zagreb energy of a graph in terms of order, independence number, M_{2r-1} , and R_r .

Theorem 15. *Let G be a connected graph with $n \geq 2$ vertices and independence number α . Then*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \leq 2\sqrt{(n - \alpha)(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)}.$$

Proof. Let $\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_p$, be the p positive eigenvalues of Z_1^r and let $\nu_1, \nu_2, \dots, \nu_q$, be the q negative eigenvalues of Z_1^r . Then Z_1^r has $n - p - q$ eigenvalues which are equal to zero. From Lemma 6, we have

$$\alpha \leq (n - p - q) + \min\{p, q\}.$$

Thus $\alpha \leq (n - p - q) + p$ and $\alpha \leq (n - p - q) + q$. Namely, $p \leq n - \alpha$ and $q \leq n - \alpha$.

Since $\sum_{i=1}^p \mu_i + \sum_{i=1}^q \nu_i = 0$, we have that

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) = 2 \sum_{i=1}^p \mu_i = 2 \sum_{i=1}^q |\nu_i|.$$

From Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, we have that

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) = 2 \sum_{i=1}^p \mu_i \leq 2 \sqrt{p \sum_{i=1}^p \mu_i}.$$

Analogously above, we get the following inequality

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) = 2 \sum_{i=1}^q \nu_i \leq 2 \sqrt{q \sum_{i=1}^q \nu_i}.$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(E(Z_1^r(G)))^2}{2} &= \frac{(E(Z_1^r(G)))^2}{4} + \frac{(E(Z_1^r(G)))^2}{4} \leq p \sum_{i=1}^p \mu_i^2 + q \sum_{i=1}^q \nu_i^2 \\ &\leq (n - \alpha) \sum_{i=1}^p \mu_i^2 + (n - \alpha) \sum_{i=1}^q \nu_i^2 \\ &= (n - \alpha) \left(\sum_{i=1}^p \mu_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^q \nu_i^2 \right) \\ &= 2(n - \alpha)(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the theorem. □

We now provide a relation among the general Zagreb energy, order, M_{2r-1} and R_r .

Theorem 16. *Let G be a graph with n vertices. Then*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \leq \sqrt{n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r) - \frac{n}{2}(|\mu_1| - |\mu_n|)^2}. \tag{15}$$

Proof. From the Lagrange’s identity (see, for example, [15]), we have

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r) - (E(Z_1^r(G)))^2 &= \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|\right)^2 \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} (|\mu_i| - |\mu_j|)^2, \end{aligned}$$

which implies the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r) - (E(Z_1^r(G)))^2 &\geq \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} \left((|\mu_1| - |\mu_i|)^2 + (|\mu_i| - |\mu_n|)^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (|\mu_1| - |\mu_n|)^2 \right). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, from the Jensen’s inequality (see [16]), we have

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r) - (E(Z_1^r(G)))^2 &\geq \frac{n-2}{2} (|\mu_1| - |\mu_n|)^2 + (|\mu_1| - |\mu_n|)^2 \\ &= \frac{n}{2} (|\mu_1| - |\mu_n|)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging the terms in the above inequality, we have (15). □

The following results relate the general Zagreb energy and M_{2r-1} and R_r .

Theorem 17. *Let G be a graph with n vertices. and $|\mu_1| \geq |\mu_2| \geq \dots \geq |\mu_n|$ be the eigenvalues of Z_1^r . Then the following inequality is valid*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \geq \sqrt{n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r) - \theta(n)(|\mu_1| - |\mu_n|)^2}. \tag{16}$$

where $\theta(n) = n[\frac{n}{2}](1 - \frac{1}{n}[\frac{n}{2}])$, while $[x]$ denotes integer part of a real number x .

Proof. Let $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ and $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ be real numbers for which there exist real constants a, b, A and B , so that for each $i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, $a \leq a_i \leq A$ and $b \leq b_i \leq B$. Then the following inequality is valid (see [1])

$$\left| n \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i - \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \sum_{i=1}^n b_i \right| \leq \theta(n)(A - a)(B - b). \tag{17}$$

Equality in (17) holds if and only if $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_n$ and $b_1 = b_2 = \dots = b_n$. For $a_i := |\mu_i|$, $b_i := |\mu_i|$, $a = b := |\mu_n|$ and $A = B := |\mu_1|$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ inequality (17) becomes

$$\left| n \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i| \right)^2 \right| \leq \theta(n)(|\mu_1| - |\mu_n|)^2.$$

Therefore, the above inequality becomes

$$n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r) - (E(Z_1^r(G)))^2 \leq \theta(n)(|\mu_1| - |\mu_n|)^2,$$

where from the statement of Theorem 17 follows. Since equality in (17) holds if and only if $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_n$ and $b_1 = b_2 = \dots = b_n$, equality in (16) holds if and only if $|\mu_1| = |\mu_2| = \dots = |\mu_n|$. $\square$

The next result concerns the general Zagreb energy of graphs in terms of M_{2r-1} , R_r an order of G .

Theorem 18. *Let G be a graph with n vertices and $|\mu_1| \geq |\mu_2| \geq \dots \geq |\mu_n|$ be a non-increasing arrangement of eigenvalues of G . Then, the following inequality is valid*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \geq \frac{|\mu_1||\mu_n|n + 2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r}{|\mu_1| + |\mu_n|}. \tag{18}$$

Equality in (18) holds if and only if $G \cong \bar{K}_n$.

Proof. Let $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ and $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ be real numbers for which there exist real constants R and r , so that for each $i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, holds $ra_i \leq b_i \leq Ra_i$. Then the following inequality is valid (see [5])

$$\sum_{i=1}^n b_i^2 + rR \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^2 \leq (r + R) \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i. \tag{19}$$

Equality in (19) holds if and only if for at least one $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ holds $ra_i = b_i = Ra_i$. For $a_i := 1$, $b_i := |\mu_i|$, $r := |\mu_n|$ and $R := |\mu_1|$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, inequality (19) becomes

$$\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 + |\mu_1||\mu_n| \sum_{i=1}^n 1 \leq (|\mu_n| + |\mu_1|) \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|.$$

Therefore, the above inequality becomes

$$n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r) + n|\mu_1||\mu_n| \leq (|\mu_n| + |\mu_1|)E(Z_1^r(G)).$$

If for some i holds that $ra_i = b_i = \mu_i$, then for the same i also holds $b_i = r = R$. This means that for each $j, j \neq i$ holds $|\mu_j| \leq |\mu_i|$. Therefore equality in (19) holds if and only if $|\mu_1| = |\mu_2| = \dots = |\mu_n|$. $\square$

The next theorem reveals a connection between the general Zagreb energy and N_k .

Theorem 19. *Let G be a non-empty graph with n vertices. Then*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \geq \frac{(N_2)^2}{N_4}.$$

Proof. We start with the Hölder inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n b_i^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}, \tag{20}$$

which holds for non-negative real numbers $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ and $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$. Setting $a_i = |\mu_i|^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $b_i = |\mu_i|^{\frac{3}{2}}$, $p = 2$ and $q = 2$, from (20), we obtain

$$\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^{\frac{1}{2}} (|\mu_i|^3)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i| \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \tag{21}$$

Then $\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^3 \neq 0$ and (21) can be written as the following

$$\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i| \geq \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 \right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^3} \geq \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i|^2 \right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_i)^4}.$$

This implies the result stated in the theorem. □

Now, we give a lower bound for the general Zagreb energy.

Theorem 20. *Let G be a non-empty graph with n vertices. Then*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \geq \frac{\sqrt{8n(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)(|\mu_1||\mu_n|)}}{|\mu_1| + |\mu_n|}.$$

Proof. Let $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ and $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ be real numbers for which there exist real constants m_1, m_2, M'_1 and M'_2 , so that for each $i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, $m_1 \leq a_i \leq M'_1$ and $m_2 \leq b_i \leq M'_2$. Then the following inequality is valid by the Hölder inequality (see [12], p. 135)

$$\left[\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i)^2 \right] \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (b_i)^2 \right] \leq \frac{1}{4} \left(\sqrt{\frac{M'_1 M'_2}{m_1 m_2}} + \sqrt{\frac{m_1 m_2}{M'_1 M'_2}} \right)^2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \right)^2 \tag{22}$$

where the equality holds if and only if $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_n$, $b_1 = b_2 = \dots = b_n$, $m_1 = M'_1 = a_1$, $m_2 = M'_2 = b_1$.

For $a_i := |\mu_i|$, $b_i := 1$, $m_1 := |\mu_n|$, $M'_1 := |\mu_1|$, $M'_2 = m_2 := 1$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, inequality (22) becomes

$$\left[\sum_{i=1}^n (|\mu_i|)^2 \right] \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (1)^2 \right] \leq \frac{1}{4} \left(\sqrt{\frac{|\mu_1|}{|\mu_n|}} + \sqrt{\frac{|\mu_n|}{|\mu_1|}} \right)^2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i| \right)^2. \tag{23}$$

Thus the above inequality is equivalent to

$$n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r) \leq \frac{1}{4} \left(\sqrt{\frac{|\mu_1|}{|\mu_n|}} + \sqrt{\frac{|\mu_n|}{|\mu_1|}} \right)^2 (E(Z_1^r(G)))^2,$$

that is

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \geq \frac{\sqrt{8n(M_{2r-1} + 2R_r)(|\mu_1||\mu_n|)}}{|\mu_1| + |\mu_n|}.$$

□

In the next theorem, we determine an upper bound for the general Zagreb energy.

Theorem 21. *Let G be a graph with n vertices. Then*

$$E(Z_1^r(G)) \leq \sqrt[3]{n^2} \sqrt{2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r}.$$

Proof. Let $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$, $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n$ and $c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n$, be positive real numbers, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Then the following inequality is valid by the Hölder inequality (see [12], p. 137)

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i c_i \right)^3 \leq \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i)^3 \right] \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (b_i)^3 \right] \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (c_i)^3 \right], \tag{24}$$

where equality holds if and only if $a_i = b_i = c_i$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. For $a_i := |\mu_i|$, $b_i := 1$, $c_i := 1$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, inequality (24) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_i| \right)^3 &\leq \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (|\mu_i|)^3 \right] \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (1)^3 \right] \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (1)^3 \right] \\ &= n^2 \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (|\mu_i|)^3 \right] \\ &\leq n^2 \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (|\mu_i|)^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{2}}, \quad \text{by Inequality (5)} \\ &= n^2 \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_i)^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{2}} \\ &= n^2 [2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r]^{\frac{3}{2}}, \quad \text{by Equality (4)}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies the result stated in the theorem.

□

In [17], the authors proved the following result.

Theorem 22. [17] *If P is an $n \times n$ matrix with real eigenvalues and n is odd, then*

$$s^2(P) \geq 2 \left(\frac{\text{trc}(P^2)}{n} - \left(\frac{\text{trc}(P)}{n} \right)^2 \right).$$

Applying this bound to the general first Zagreb matrix and considering the Lemma 1, we have following result.

Theorem 23. *Let G be a graph of order n . Then*

$$s(Z_1^r) \geq \sqrt{\frac{4M_{2r-1} + 8R_r}{n}}.$$

In [20] the authors proved the followings result for spread involves traces.

Theorem 24. [20] *If P is an $n \times n$ matrix with real eigenvalues and n is odd, then*

$$s^2(P) \geq 2 \left(\frac{n \text{trc}(P^2) - (\text{trc}(P))^2}{n^2 - 1} \right).$$

Identity P with $Z_1^r(G)$, we have the following result.

Theorem 25. *Let G be a graph of order n . Then*

$$s(Z_1^r) \geq \sqrt{\frac{n(4M_{2r-1} + 8R_r)}{n^2 - 1}}.$$

Using Inequality (8) , we can obtain the next upper and lower bounds for the spread of $Z_1^r(G)$.

Theorem 26. *Let G be a graph of order n . Then*

$$\sqrt{\frac{n(2M_{2r-1} + 4R_r)}{\binom{n}{2} \binom{n+1}{2}}} \leq s(Z_1^r) \leq \sqrt{4M_{2r-1} + 8R_r}.$$

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